

Magnetic Susceptibilities of Cobaltic Salts and the Nature of the Cobaltic Ion.

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Though it has long been established that all complex cobaltic compounds are diamagnetic, the susceptibility value for the simple Co^{++} is, however, not definitely known, due evidently to the difficulty of preparing simple cobaltic salts in the pure and solid state. The only measurement, recorded in literature, refers to a solution of cobaltic sulphate prepared by anodic oxidation of cobaltous sulphate solution (Weber, *Ann. Physik*, 1911, **36**, 624), which, as the author himself admits, was far from pure. The value obtained was about 16.73 Weiss's magneton. Wilson, also, obtained a value of 12.9 Weiss's magneton for Co_2O_3 (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1921, **A**, **98**, 274). But as Co_2O_3 can seldom be obtained in a pure state, free from other oxides of cobalt, apart from the fact that black sulphides and oxides of metals often assume metallic character and show a much lower susceptibility value than that of the free corresponding ions (Klemm and Schüth, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **203**, 104 ; 1933, **210**, 43), it was considered of special interest to determine, if possible, a more or less exact value for this ion. We have prepared a number of apparently simple cobaltic salts in the solid state and have measured their susceptibility values. They all approximate to 2 Bohr's magneton number, a value which Weber's measurement in solution tends to approach. The salts examined are anhydrous and hydrated cobaltic cyanide, cobaltic sulphate and cobaltic alum.

It is well known that the susceptibility value for the Co^{++} is given by 23.25 Weiss's magneton, or approximately 4 Bohr's magneton. The ionic susceptibilities of the elements of the first transitional series are given more or less satisfactorily by the expression,

$$p = 4.97 \sqrt{4S(S+1)}$$

according to Bose and Stoner (Bose, *Z. Physik*, 1927, **48**, 864; Stoner, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 250), where p = Weiss's magneton

number and S = resultant spin moment, the resultant orbital moment, L , is rendered ineffective due to strong interaction with the neighbouring ions. The actual experimental values and those calculated on the basis of the above formula are shown in the following figure.

No. of extranuclear electrons.

[Calculated moments are given by the curve. The thick vertical lines indicate the range of observed values.]

The first half of the series shows quite good agreement, the last half, on the other hand, reveals an appreciable deviation (actual values being higher), and the moments of the ions in this half extend over a short range suggesting that the L -interaction may take place to different extents in different compounds and is not strong enough to render the L -moment completely inoperative.

On this view, the Co^{+++} with an extranuclear electron number of 24 should possess a magnetic moment of 24.4 Weiss's magneton (4 Bohr's magneton), or a little higher than this, due to imperfect L -interaction. The actual value, obtained in the case of above cobaltic compounds, is, however, equal to 2 Bohr's magneton approximately. This is quite anomalous and demands a satisfactory explanation.

In the first place, it may be suggested that the compounds do not possess a simple constitution. Thus, for instance, $\text{Co}(\text{CN})_3$ and its hydrate may be regarded as a complex cobaltic cobalticyanide $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6]$. The complex anion, as is well known, being diamagnetic, the magnetic moment of the molecule will be contributed by only one of the Co-atoms in the free ionic state as Co^{+++} . Hence the atomic or ionic moment should come out as half the theoretical value.

On the other hand, there is little evidence or justification to assume that cobaltic sulphate and cobaltic alum, also, are made up of complex anions of the perfect order, represented as $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{SO}_4)_3]$. But, as the cobaltic alum is isomorphous with other alums, it must possess a similar composition and constitution. Further, the normal chemical behaviour of these two substances militate against the assumption of any complexity of high order in their molecule. They should consequently be regarded as simple and double salt respectively, and their magnetic moment represents the true value for the simple Co^{++} ion. But this, again, raises a question of great theoretical interest, as the observed moment is about half the expected theoretical value, even allowing for the perfect or complete L -interaction.

The Co^{+++} ion, however, is extremely unstable, readily changing into Co^{++} by the capture of an electron. Hence the electronic structure of the unstable Co^{+++} cannot represent its deepest state. The fundamental spectral terms for the two ions, Co^{++} and Co^{+++} , should be ^4F and ^5D respectively, the corresponding electronic groups being d^7 and d^6 . This should give a moment of at least 4 Bohr's magneton for the Co^{+++} identical with that for Fe^{++} , which is, however, not the case. This seems to suggest that the Co^{+++} in the above mentioned cobaltic salts is in an excited or metastable state, which should be represented by a spectral term other than ^5D . In other words, the electronic state of the Co^{++} seems to persist in the Co^{+++} , even after the removal of an additional unbalanced electron by oxidation, no redistribution of electrons, leading to the lowest energy state, occurring during the transformation of Co^{++} into Co^{+++} ion. This would give a triplet term for Co^{+++} . Hence $S=1$, and $p=4.97\sqrt{4 \times 1 \times 2}=14.01$. This is in very good agreement with the experimental values.

It may, therefore, be concluded that in these cobaltic salts the cobaltic ion is in a metastable or higher energy state, which accounts for its instability and anomalous magnetic moment.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cobaltic cyanides.—Both the red hydrated and the blue anhydrous compounds were prepared according to the method described by Rây and Gupta-Chaudhury (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 220, 162).

Blue anhydrous. [Found: Co, 42.9; CN, 57.2. $\text{Co}(\text{CN})_3$ requires Co, 43.1; CN, 56.9 per cent]. $\chi_m(t_{31})=22.31 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{\text{Weiss}}=13.58$; p_{Weiss} corrected = 13.63.

Red hydrated. [Found: Co, 34.22; H₂O, 20.60. Co (CN)₃, 2H₂O requires Co, 34.10; H₂O, 20.81 per cent]. $\chi_m(t_{30}) = 21.79 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{air}} = 15.04$; $p_{W_{air}}$ corrected = 15.16.

Cobaltic alum was prepared according to the method described by Marshall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891 59, 760) by electrolysis in a divided cell in the cold. The large blue crystals were removed, rapidly dried by means of filter paper and examined at once in a Curie's balance. [Found: Co, 11.98. Co₂(SO₄)₃.(NH₄)₂SO₄.24H₂O requires Co, 12.16 per cent]. $\chi_m(t_{31}) = 0.48 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{air}} = 13.76$; $p_{W_{air}}$ corrected = 14.29.

Cobaltic sulphate was prepared by electrolysis in the cold in a divided cell as described by Copeaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1905 140, 657). The blue crystals were dried and examined as before. $\chi_m(t_{30}) = 11.28 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{air}} = 15.71$; $p_{W_{air}}$ corrected = 16.05.

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The Complex Formation between Manganese or Aluminium with Tartaric Acid in Alkaline Medium.

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The present work is in continuation of the work carried out by Raman and Vaishya on complex formation between cerium or tungsten with tartaric acid in alkaline media (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 179).

EXPERIMENTAL.

In order to work with manganese chloride and potassium tartrate in alkaline solution and to ensure that no precipitate is formed under ordinary circumstances, it is found to be essential to add only sufficient quantity of alkali so that the whole of the manganese salt is transformed into hydroxide and there is only slight